

Table S2. Climate variable abbreviations, definitions, and units.

Abbreviation	ClimateNA variable	Units
AHM	Annual heat-moisture index $(MAT+10)/(MAP/1000)$	°C/m
CMD	Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit	mm
DD_0	Degree-days below 0°C, chilling degree-days	dd
DD5	Degree days above 5°C, growing degree-days	dd
EMT	Extreme minimum temperature over 30 years	°C
Eref	Hargreaves reference evaporation	mm
EXT	Extreme maximum temperature over 30 years	°C
FFP	Frost-free period	days
MAP	Mean annual precipitation	mm
MAT	Mean annual temperature	°C
MCMT	Mean coldest month temperature	°C
MSP	Mean summer precipitation [May to September]	mm
MWMT	Mean warmest month temperature	°C
PAS	Precipitation as snow [August to July]	mm
SHM	Summer heat-moisture index $(MWMT)/(MSP/1000)$	°C/m
TD	Temperature difference between MWMT and MCMT, or continentality	°C